
9. Gaia and GDP

WHAT CONDITIONS exist in our society that allow expensive high-technology projects like Gaia to be undertaken in the first place? Why do funding agencies support these huge efforts? What are the returns for society, not only intellectually, but more generally?

ARGUMENTS THAT can be put forward for major investments in space missions include:

- scientific: scientists often argue that the search for the underlying laws of physics, and a deeper understanding of the Universe, are strong arguments for investment and research for any advanced and civilised society;
- unexpected spin-offs: as an extension of the pursuit of ‘pure research’, entirely unexpected and unpredictable spin-offs can eventually deliver substantial benefits to society, with associated economic dividends;
- applied spin-offs: more calculated approaches to exploiting potential spin-offs arising from space research can be encouraged and coordinated through technology transfer programmes and business ‘incubation’;
- technology development: space exploration provides new and inspiring challenges, requiring the direct development of new technologies;
- industrial: related to technology and economic return is the strong industrial interest in developing large-scale facilities and capabilities for space exploration;
- political: space exploration spectacularly demonstrates national and international capabilities, and can foster international cooperation in ambitious projects on an unprecedented scale, underpinning the ‘peace-keeping’ aspects of international collaboration;
- societal and cultural: space exploration offers extraordinary appeal to the public worldwide. It raises public interest, inspires and develops scientific culture to new levels, and attracts young people toward scientific and technical careers;
- economic: technological developments create new possibilities for innovation and economic growth, spanning business opportunities for industry as well as access to new resources.

THE DRIVERS are evidently a complex mix of science, technology, politics, and economics. But it is the last of these, the economic consequences, that I will focus on here – I imagine that economic considerations ultimately provide the strongest motivation for politicians, and so tax-payers, to commit to their very high costs.

Scientists often argue that knowledge is important for its own sake, and can be more vague when it comes to the wider benefits for society. But such arguments are easy to ignore, and budgets for space science can readily be scaled-back in the face of other priorities.

Naturally, basic scientific research (including astronomy and astrophysics) cannot be decoupled from questions of affordability, value for society, and industrial development and return.

So while we can see that Gaia is already having a major impact on scientific knowledge, we can also ask: will it have any beneficial effect on the economies of the countries that have been involved?

I will attempt a very general view of how fundamental research feeds through to economic growth.

SPACE IS NOW widely recognised as an essential resource for our civilisation, providing key services for telecommunications, satellite navigation, environmental monitoring, meteorology, crisis management, and science. Accordingly, it is widely supported by governments and private operators.

What are some headline numbers? In 2013, when Gaia was launched, Euroconsult indicated a space expenditure of €200 billion worldwide, with US government spending some \$40 billion. In 2020, the same organisation valued the space economy at \$385 billion, with commercial revenues totaling over \$310 billion.

Across Europe in 2013, the space sector was generating civil and military sales of some €5.5 billion, and employing around 33 000 people. Governments of Japan, China, France, Germany, Italy, India and the EU each invested more than \$1 billion in space activities.

Many more details along these lines are given annually, for example, by Euroconsult, and by Eurospace, the trade association of the European space industry.

IN MOST EUROPEAN countries, space programmes are contracted out to national industries. And since the 1960s, economists have tried to measure the economic impact of these programmes with a variety of tools.

As one example, the Bureau d'Économie Théorique et Appliquée (BETA) of the University of Strasbourg attempted to evaluate the indirect industrial ('spinoff') effects of projects carried out by the European Space Agency (Cohendet 1999). One of their goals was to obtain quantitative figures that could be used to evaluate the effectiveness of any particular programme in order to justify their public-sector financial commitments.

ALONG SOMEWHAT similar lines, and with similar goals, analysis by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development has estimated the economic return on investments in space across Europe (e.g. OECD Space Forum, 2011). The study attempted to answer the simple question: what is the return on investments in the space sector?

Skipping over numerous caveats, they gave the following figures for 2009: in Norway, an investment of NOK 1 million provided a return of some NOK 4.7 million. In Denmark, €1 million of Danish contributions to ESA generated a turnover of €3.7 million. In the UK, the space industry's value-added multiplier was estimated to be 1.91. In the US commercial space transportation industry, the factor was 4.9. At the upper end of the scale, NASA claimed a 7:1 return for every US dollar spent in the space programme.

It is not easy to assess what this all means precisely, but it goes in the direction of trying to quantify the argument that national investment in space yields economic as well as societal and cultural benefits.

BUT NOW LET me turn to the more specific question: is there a link between *basic research* and prosperity? Here, the distinction between basic research and applied 'research and development' is essentially a distinction between discovering the laws of nature, and harnessing them for practical purposes.

A more considered definition is given in the OECD's *Frascati Manual for Research and Development Statistics* (2002, p30). Basic research is defined there as: '*experimental or theoretical work undertaken primarily to acquire new knowledge of the underlying foundation of phenomena and observable facts, without any particular application or use in view*'. Applied research is defined as: '*directed primarily towards a specific practical aim or objective*'.

It is not difficult to find numbers used in arguments for funding basic research. For example, the then President of the Max Planck Society, Peter Gruss, argued in the *Max Planck Magazine*, in 2012: '*80% of economic growth in the industrialised countries results from the development of new technologies. And it is research, after all, that contributes vital ideas for new technologies*'.

WHERE DO SUCH numbers come from? While more traditional economic theories seem to ignore the role of basic research in economic prosperity, attempts have been made more recently to quantify their link.

In the class of economic theories characterised by 'endogenous growth', technological progress is generated by the accumulation of knowledge. An important result of these models is that growth is strongly dependent on spending on *basic* research, and indeed ceases without it (e.g. van Bochove, 2012).

Although much has been written on the subject, there is no simple answer. The absence of a clear consensus is probably reflected in the varying percentage of gross national product that is spent on space R&D by each country, and their contribution to ESA.

Again, estimates by Euroconsult indicated that, in 2013, the annual expenditure on space per capita ranged from \$12 (0.03% of GNP) in the UK, \$19 (0.04%) in Germany, \$17 (0.05%) in Italy, \$44 (0.10%) in France, and all the way up to \$150 (0.32%) in the US.

That basic research is likely to be an indispensable catalyst for wealth and societal advance was at the heart of the Lisbon Strategy, an action and development plan set out by the European Council in March 2000, for the economy of the EU between 2000–2010. Through various policy initiatives, its aim was to make the EU '*the most competitive and dynamic knowledge-based economy in the world capable of sustainable economic growth with more and better jobs and greater social cohesion*'.

WHILE THE connection between research funding (both pure and applied) and economic growth seems to be plausible, and arguably convincing, the details remain imperfectly understood. Nonetheless, demanding that a research proposal must be able to demonstrate a *direct link* between the research and its economic benefits, would perhaps seem misguided.

Gaia started on its path as an idea that two scientists sat down and discussed in Leiden in 1993. During its technical development, it involved thousands of scientists, engineers, and managers across dozens of European industries. Its exploitation now involves hundreds of scientists, both career professionals as well as early-stage researchers who will move on to positions in science, industry, education, and management.

Can we then argue that Gaia is bringing significant economic returns as well as enormous scientific advances? I suspect so, but I have no quantitative evidence to support such a claim!

THESE CONSIDERATIONS were part of my contribution to a study undertaken in 2014 by the European Academies Science Advisory Council (EASAC), chaired by Thierry Courvoisier, and which were included in its final report '*Strategic Considerations of Human versus Robotic Exploration*'.